

An Empirical Survey of GitHub Repositories at U.S. R2 and Doctoral/Professional Universities

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Abstract—Understanding the landscape of Research Software Engineering (RSE) projects, and basic information about RSE repositories such as how many are out there to begin with, is an area of discovery ripe for scholarship. We position this five page short paper, which focuses on US universities with “R2” or “Doctoral/Professional” Carnegie classifications, as a modest intermediary step in a multi-paper arc examining RSE repositories in a variety of research contexts; an arc which has previously examined RSE repositories in the US National Laboratory system and R1 universities. In this work we report to the community our findings on these research questions: What are all the GitHub repositories related to US R2 and Doctoral/Professional universities? Of those, which are RSE projects? Which of these RSE projects have communities larger than just the core authors? How healthy are they? And how do all of the above questions compare to the R1 university context? We find there are both fewer GitHub repositories and fewer RSE repositories at R2 than at R1 institutions, and fewer at doctoral universities than at R2s. Of these fewer RSE projects at R2s and doctoral universities, more of them had a community than RSE projects at R1 universities. While R1 and doctoral universities have similar profiles of healthy/dying/dead repositories, R2 RSE repositories are less likely to be active and more likely to be dead. We also include the number of RSE repositories associated with each R2 and Doctoral/Professional university as a five page appendix.

Index Terms—Empirical survey, R2 universities, doctoral universities, research software engineering, GitHub, repositories

I. INTRODUCTION

The sub field of research software engineering (RSE), as an area of scholarly inquiry in its own right, is in its infancy. Broad questions like, “*Just how many research software projects are out there anyway? Empirically speaking, what do they look like?*” continue to be ripe for answering. In this paper we expand on earlier work presented at US-RSE 2024 [1], which explored and inventoried open source software projects hosted on GitHub with some nexus to US research universities, as determined by 2021 Carnegie “R1” research university classification. We apply nearly identical methodology to uncover and assess RSE repositories, but point to a different part of academia: namely, the R2 and professional doctoral universities in the United States, which, as hotbeds of research activity too, we suspect also contain a good number of RSE software projects.

The research questions which guide this work are:

- RQ1 What are all of the public software projects / repositories on GitHub with some nexus – even a weak one – to the “R2” and “Professional/Doctoral” American universities? (Where “R2” and “Professional/Doctoral” are as defined by a university’s 2021 Carnegie classification.)
- RQ2 Of these software projects with some sort of nexus to a research university, which ones are RSE projects?
- RQ3 Of the RSE projects / repositories found through answering RQ2, which ones are likely to be popular outside of the project’s core developers? That is, which projects are used by the community – either a university-internal community, or external/world-at-large community?
- RQ4 Of the RSE projects / repositories used by the community, which are still actively developed or maintained? Are there unmaintained projects with community use? If so, do we have any sense of what skills are needed to maintain them?

In answering these questions about R2 and professional doctoral universities through previously established exploratory approaches, we also provide side-by-side comparisons with the findings presented about R1 universities in [1]. As noted in [1], we continue to look forward to examining non US universities, industry research labs, repository sources other than GitHub – and within GitHub non-repository pages (e.g., institute owner pages) – and so forth in future papers.

II. RELATED WORK

Our work is fundamentally grounded in the landmark 2002 paper, *What Makes Good Research in Software Engineering?* by Mary Shaw [2]. Our research questions fall under Shaw’s “Design, evaluation, or analysis of a particular instance” (e.g., “What is the current state of X?”) and “Generalization or characterization” (e.g., “What are the varieties of X and how are they related?”) categories of good research questions. In general, scholarly work around the empirical analysis and classification of scientific and research software engineering, particularly when segmented by sector (e.g., academia, national laboratories, industry), is very nascent [1], [3]–[5]. Nevertheless, there is some work that has already

been done. This paper, focused on US R2 and professional doctoral universities, builds off of previous work examining RSE repositories in the U.S. National Laboratory system [5] and R1 universities in [1] and mirrors the methodology closely. Besides [1], we note the following works related to each of our research questions.

Related to RQ1: Outside of the United States, Carlin et al. [6] examined United Kingdom academic institutional repositories for software prevalence, finding that, “Fewer than 28% contain software as recognised academic output.” Adjacently, Garijo et al. [7] explored the relationship between bidirectional paper-repository tracing (primarily through ArXiv mining) and the non-trivial challenges involved therein. Earlier work was done by Wattanakriengkrai et al. [8], tracing links in papers to GitHub. Related to RQ2: Zanatru et al. [9] observed that using NLP to categorize the application domain of a GitHub repository had around 70% accuracy, a trend in line with (although slightly lower than) [1]’s findings of accuracy around ChatGPT correctly identifying a given GitHub repository as being an RSE repository between 77-90%. Related to RQ3 and RQ4: Work by Borges et al. [10] and Moid et al. [11] investigated the factors which impact GitHub repositories, such as their number of stars and forks, while Biazzi et al. [12] investigated collaboration metrics, many of which are adjacent to repository’ community vibrancy and thus sustainability.

III. RQ1: PROJECTS WITH A NEXUS TO R2 AND “PROFESSIONAL DOCTORAL” UNIVERSITIES

What are all of the public software projects / repositories on GitHub with some nexus – even a weak one – to the “R2” and “Professional/Doctoral” American universities?

A. Definitions, Initial Scope, Overarching Approach:

As an extension of [1], our goal is to continue to cast a wide net in looking for research software projects related to academic research institutions but within roughly the same parameters. We limit ourselves to GitHub due to public availability, leaving the interrogation of other code / version control management systems (e.g., Subversion) and other locally managed systems (e.g., privately hosted git servers) as future work.

We identified all “R2” and “doctoral/professional” universities from data provided by the 2023 US federal government’s Integrated Postsecondary Education Data System (IPEDS), which in turn is based on the 2021 Carnegie system of institutional classifications. IPEDS also contained a clean data set of uniform information, such as official websites and nicknames/aliases for universities, as provided to the federal government by the universities themselves on an annual basis as a condition for receiving federal funding. We note that the most recent Carnegie classifications were released in Spring 2025, after we had commenced work on this paper. Further, as an extension to [1], we note that there would be some shifting in institutions between R1 and R2 status, making any comparisons between the two groups

fuzzier. Moreover, the Carnegie Foundation and American Council on Education redefined the underlying criteria for R1, R2, etc., classification in 2025, thus further muddying the waters for direct comparison. Consequentially, it made sense for us to use the same 2021 classifications in this paper. As for the continued use of the 2023 IPEDS data, the 2024 IPEDS data has not been released yet.¹

With this data, we took two approaches. (1) Run a web crawling “spider” that looks for links to GitHub across the websites of every R2 and doctoral university and (2) search GitHub itself for keywords related to these universities. We dive deeper into each approach below.

B. Approach 1: Scraping university websites

We excluded R2 universities which shared the same domain name with an R1 university, and doctoral universities which shared a URL with either an R1 or R2 university. An example of an R2 university which shares their domain name with an R1 is Arizona State University – Digital Immersion. While colloquially this is ASU online, and shares R1 ASU’s asu.edu domain name, it’s legally structured as an independent campus with R2 status in its own right. Similarly, the Rutgers university system legally contains three separate universities in New Jersey (one R1, two R2s) also share the rutgers.edu domain. In all, only five R2 and four doctoral universities fell into these situations and we proceeded to continue with a total of 128 R2 universities and 181 doctoral universities as our base data set. We note that this means these nine R2 and doctoral universities are implicitly included in the R1 findings of [1].

In spring of 2025 we deployed our webcrawling spider on each R2 and doctoral institution’s website, as reported in the IPEDS data. The spider ran until all reachable HTML links on a website had been traversed, or for a maximum of 200 hours, and used a breadth-first-search traversal approach. We strive to be good netizens, so our spider also obeyed the robots.txt file of each institution. We then cleaned, shortened, and filtered these links to match the pattern `github.com/owner/repository`, with duplicates consolidated.

1) *Results, and Comparison with R1 Universities:* Of the 128 R2 universities with unique URLs, 95 (75%) had `robot.txt` files which permitted web scraping of any sort on their domains. Of the 181 doctoral universities with unique URLs, 119 (66%) were able to be scraped without error. This compares with 70% of R1 universities. 29,675,754 different URLs were traversed for R2 universities, an average of 231,842 per institution. Excluding one university outlier², there were a total of 14,002,051 URLs traversed across the

¹We note news media reporting that the federal government has fired at least half of all employees at the National Center for Education Statistics, which compiles the IPEDS data. insidehighered.com/news/students/academics/2025/03/14/layoffs-gut-federal-education-research-agency, abcnews.go.com/Politics/education-department-cuts-agency-compiles-nations-report-card/story?id=119735831

²The outlier, cuw.edu, had an unusual URL linking redirect structure that padded an additional 26,668,643 URLs to the count. No links to GitHub repositories were found.

doctoral/professional universities, an average of 118,661 pages per institution. R1 universities, by contrast, had larger web footprints, with an average of 384,195 crawlable webpages per institution. Results about the number of repositories found on institutional webpages are summarized in Table I.

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF THE NUMBER OF UNIQUE REPOSITORIES FOUND THROUGH LINKS POSTED ON R1, R2, AND DOCTORAL/PROFESSIONAL UNIVERSITY WEBSITES WHICH PERMITTED WEB SCRAPING.

Comparison Group	R1s	R2s	Doctoral
Number of institutions in group	116	95	152
Mean number of URLs scraped per institutional website	384k	232k	119k
Minimum number of unique repositories found on an institutional website.	0	0	0
Mean number of unique repositories found on institutional websites	58	2	1
Median number of unique repositories found on institutional websites	16	7	0
Maximum number of unique repositories found on an institutional website	951	138	11

There were a combined total of 657 unique repositories found across the webpages of all R2 websites. For doctoral universities, there were only 60. This compares with 10,056 found in [1] for R1 universities.

C. Approach 2: Searching on GitHub

In addition to scouring websites, we also used GitHub’s search functionality to find GitHub repositories related to universities by doing keyword searches, where the keywords were derived from IPEDS data. Specifically, for each university for which there was a successful webscraping, we searched for the following terms using GitHub’s search API: the official university name, the domain name of the university, the domain name of the university sans “.edu,” and the individual aliases for the school reported by the institution itself in the IPEDS data. The search API, which is case insensitive, returns the same results as manually searching on GitHub’s website. We limited ourselves to the first 1,000 results on GitHub for each keyword, which is the maximum number of results the API returns in one call.

1) *Results and Comparison with R1 Universities:* Across all examined R2 universities, 73,080 possible RSE GitHub repositories were returned by searching for keywords. These ranged from 18 repositories at the University of South Alabama to 2,852 at Texas State. The mean and median were 759 and 1,003, respectively.

For doctoral universities, there were 82,280 possible RSE repositories in total. These ranged from 1 found repository (`github.com/Orissa324/caluniversity`) at California Intercontinental University whose website is `caluniversity.edu`, to 3,992 at Regis University, with a mean and median of 706 and 661, respectively.

This compares to 187,728 repositories found through keyword searches at 116 R1 universities, an average of 1,618 per institution.

Of course, just because a link to a GitHub repository was posted on a university website somewhere, or a repository turned up in a keyword search related to a university, does not mean the repository in question is, in fact, an RSE repository. Indeed, the single repository found by keyword searches around by terms related to California Intercontinental University is an empty repository, with no files whatsoever, for example. This brings us to our second research question.

IV. RQ2: IS A GIVEN REPOSITORY AN RSE REPOSITORY?

Of the software projects with some sort of nexus to an R2 or doctoral university, which ones are RSE projects?

To determine whether a repository is an RSE repository at scale, we turned to OpenAI’s GPT 3.5 Large Language Model (ChatGPT), which was the model used in [1] and which methodology we again mimic identically in order to compare with R1 universities.

To recap: the definition for “RSE” came from <https://us-rse.org/about/what-is-an-rse/>. A description of each repository was created by piping the text obtained from the GitHub CLI command `gh repo view owner/repository`, which includes the repository’s name, brief description, and the contents of the README document if available. Putting it all together, the prompt followed this template:

```
.....
Consider the following definition of a Research
Software Engineer:
```

```
“We like an inclusive definition of Research
Software Engineers to encompass those who
regularly use expertise in programming to advance
research. This includes researchers who spend a
significant amount of time programming, full-time
software engineers writing code to solve research
problems, and those somewhere in-between. We
aspire to apply the skills and practices of software
development to research to create more robust,
manageable, and sustainable research software.”
```

```
Consider the following information about a Github
repository:
```

```
===
"View Repo" Data Inserted Here
===
```

```
Given the above definition and Github repository
information, is this Github repository a research
software engineering project? Report your answer
as a probability between 0 and 1. Place this number
at the end of the message.
```

.....
Due to the existing analysis and discussion undertaken in [1], we again chose 0.75 as our numerical cutoff for determining whether a GitHub repository is an RSE project.

We continue to expect an overall accuracy of around $84\% \pm 7\%$ due to using the same underlying ChatGPT 3.5 model.

There were a combined total of 659 unique repositories found while scraping R2 websites and 73,080 found from GitHub keyword searches. Unioning these two sets resulted in 73,709 possible RSE repositories with a connection to R2 universities.

For doctoral universities, there were only 60 unique repositories found through website scraping, 82,280 possible RSE repositories found through GitHub keyword searches, and a total of 82,337 possible RSE repositories to consider from across the union of both sets. (The size of the unioned search and scrape sets for R1 universities, by comparison, was 193,921 repositories.)

We then assessed whether each of these repositories for whether they were RSE repositories or not.

A. Results and Comparison with R1 Universities

Of the R2-connected repositories evaluated, 10,983 (15%) were considered to be RSE. In the doctoral case, 10,037 (12%) were identified by ChatGPT as RSE. This compares with 18% of repositories at R1 institutions.

A breakdown by R2 institution can be found in Table VII which ends on page 8 and for doctoral institutions in Table VIII which ends on page 10. A side-by-side summary comparison with R1 universities is in Table VI on page 6. Missing institutions in these tables indicate their website’s robots.txt file did not permit webscraping.

We note that during processing there were rare technical issues with obtaining data from ChatGPT for some repositories. As in the R1 case, these issues constituted well under 1% of the thousands of repositories we assessed, with the total number of errors in the low dozens across both R2 and doctoral universities. As in the R1 case, these few errors usually reflected a misnamed repository from an extracted link (resulting in a 404 error) or a binary file uploaded as a project’s README file (resulting in a character encoding error).

V. RQ3: POPULARITY OF RSE PROJECTS

Of the RSE projects / repositories found through answering RQ2, which ones are likely to be popular outside of the project’s core developers? That is, which projects are used by the community – either a university-internal community, or external/world-at-large community?

To answer this question, we queried GitHub’s API to obtain basic information about each RSE repository identified in RQ2, including the number of stars and forks. As per the discussion in [1], we define an RSE repository as having a community if it has, at bare minimum, at least six stars or six forks.

A. Results, and Comparison with R1 Universities

We found that 5,795 R2 RSE repositories met our threshold for having a community, or 52.8%. Doctoral universities had 5,101 RSE repositories with a community, or 50.8%. This compares with 39.4% of RSE repositories at R1 universities

TABLE II
NUMBER OF HEALTHY, DYING, AND DEAD RSE REPOSITORIES WITH A COMMUNITY, BY INSTITUTION CLASSIFICATION.

Comparison Group	R1s	R2s	Doctoral
Healthy	3,805 (27%)	1,200 (21%)	1,392 (27%)
Dying	3,346 (24%)	1,281 (22%)	1,138 (22%)
Dead	6,784 (49%)	3,314 (57%)	2,571 (50%)

which, in turn, was higher than at US national laboratories at 25%. [5]

The “why” behind these numbers continues to be intriguing and worth further study. We find it surprising that RSE projects at R2 and doctoral universities are more likely to have community associated with them than at R1s and US national laboratories. Understanding the human dynamics which undergird these numbers is excellent future work.

VI. RQ4: WHICH RSE PROJECTS WITH COMMUNITIES ARE ACTIVE? WHICH ARE ON LIFE SUPPORT?

Of the RSE projects / repositories used by the community, which are still actively developed or maintained? Are there unmaintained projects with community use? If so, do we have any sense of what skills are needed to maintain them?

To answer this research question, and again following the methodology in [1], we examined the “last push” date of a repository. We then categorized each as healthy if there was an update within the last six months, dying if there had not been an update in six months but more recently than two years, and dead if the repository had not been pushed to for more than two years. This is reported in Table II.

We further identified the most used programming language in each repository and report the disaggregated information by each category of healthy, dying, and dead repositories.

A. Results, and Comparison with R1 Universities

We found that R1s and doctoral universities had similar percentages of healthy/dying/dead repositories, within one or two percent of each other in each classification. However, R2s were more likely to have fewer healthy repositories and more dead repositories than R1s or doctoral universities. These findings are located in Table II. The reason for this is unclear and warrants greater investigation in future work. In any case, all categories of universities have significantly fewer healthy RSE projects (21%-27%) than at US National Laboratories (60%) [5]. We hypothesize that this may be due to funding streams and workforce allocation – e.g., salaried and experienced professional staff at a national laboratory are more likely to make regular contributions to a funded and ongoing project than (possibly unpaid) research students with graduation deadlines at a university working on a project with a dubious financial future.

We also found that Python was the most used RSE language at R1s, R2s and doctoral universities. However, we note that languages like Rust and TypeScript are more prevalent in healthy RSE repositories connected to doctoral universities than they are at R1s, forming 9% and 6% of all doctoral RSE

TABLE III
PRIMARY LANGUAGE FREQUENCY (NUMBER AND PERCENTAGE) AMONG
HEALTHY RSE REPOSITORIES, STRATIFIED BY UNIVERSITY
CLASSIFICATION. ROWS ARE SORTED BY MAX(R1%, R2%,
DOCTORAL%).

Name	R1		R2		Doctoral	
	#	%	#	%	#	%
Python	1211	33%	400	34%	393	29%
C++	472	13%	79	7%	118	9%
Rust	121	3%	49	4%	126	9%
TypeScript	95	3%	98	8%	85	6%
Jupyter Notebook	261	7%	69	6%	60	4%
C	229	6%	50	4%	70	5%
JavaScript	158	4%	42	4%	67	5%
Java	142	4%	53	5%	46	3%
Go	136	4%	32	3%	57	4%
HTML	84	2%	37	3%	25	2%
R	99	3%	32	3%	40	3%
C#	76	2%	34	3%	40	3%
Shell	72	2%	16	1%	29	2%
Ruby	43	1%	14	1%	19	1%
Julia	43	1%	16	1%	14	1%
Elixir		<1%		<1%	14	1%
MATLAB	45	1%		<1%		<1%

TABLE IV
PRIMARY LANGUAGE FREQUENCY (NUMBER AND PERCENTAGE) AMONG
DYING RSE REPOSITORIES, STRATIFIED BY UNIVERSITY CLASSIFICATION.

Name	R1		R2		Doctoral	
	#	%	#	%	#	%
Python	1285	40%	532	43%	431	40%
Jupyter Notebook	351	11%	118	10%	89	8%
C++	318	10%	78	6%	83	8%
JavaScript	165	5%	49	4%	57	5%
C	163	5%	47	4%	53	5%
TypeScript	48	1%	60	5%	26	2%
Java	120	4%	46	4%	46	4%
Rust	50	2%	29	2%	41	4%
R	70	2%	34	3%	40	4%
C#	65	2%	21	2%	34	3%
HTML	100	3%	21	2%	19	2%
Go	39	1%	29	2%	21	2%
MATLAB	73	2%	24	2%		<1%
Shell	53	2%	21	2%	21	2%

TABLE V
PRIMARY LANGUAGE FREQUENCY (NUMBER AND PERCENTAGE) AMONG
DEAD RSE REPOSITORIES, STRATIFIED BY UNIVERSITY CLASSIFICATION.

Name	R1		R2		Doctoral	
	#	%	#	%	#	%
Python	2084	32%	1217	38%	829	34%
Jupyter Notebook	780	12%	352	11%	233	10%
C++	741	11%	247	8%	231	10%
C	479	7%	166	5%	106	4%
JavaScript	305	5%	193	6%	138	6%
Java	316	5%	172	5%	103	4%
R	160	2%	45	1%	79	3%
MATLAB	181	3%	74	2%	65	3%
Matlab	163	3%	40	1%	38	2%
Shell	118	2%	52	2%	64	3%
HTML	156	2%	63	2%	53	2%
C#	125	2%	60	2%	52	2%
TypeScript		<1%	58	2%	25	1%
Go	71	1%	34	1%	38	2%
SystemVerilog		<1%	45	1%		<1%
Rust		<1%		<1%	34	1%
TeX		<1%		<1%	28	1%

repositories vs 3% and 3%, respectively. These findings are located in Tables III, IV, and V.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this work we set out to inventory RSE repositories at US R2 and doctoral/professional universities. Due to webscraping policies forbidding automated crawling on some university websites, we collected data on about 70% on all R2/doctoral universities. This aligns with the percentage of R1 universities that permitted webscraping in our comparison dataset. We found that the websites of R2 and doctoral universities tended to have fewer web pages overall than R1 universities and, as both a ratio of links to GitHub vs website pages and in raw volume, even fewer links to GitHub repositories found on institutional websites.

Of those repositories with some sort of nexus to an R2 or doctoral university an even smaller percentage of them were RSE repositories compared to the R1 case. Some R2 and doctoral universities have very few connections to software repositories of any kind, indicating a general lack of software development. Future work in this area might include automated labeling all projects (e.g., labeling a repository as an RSE project, student homework, university website source code, etc.) to better understand the composition of these repositories.

The results so far might sound intuitive: Large and well funded R1 research universities have larger websites, more GitHub repositories, and more RSE repositories than R2 or doctoral universities. However, we then found that the RSE projects that did have a connection to R2 and doctoral universities were notably more likely to have communities than at R1 institutions. On the other hand, R2 projects with communities were more likely to be dead than healthy compared to their R1 peers.

In general, the RSE repositories exhibited many of the same characteristics across R1, R2, and doctoral universities, including in star and fork distribution shape and most commonly used programming language (Python, Jupyter Notebook, and C++ take the cake). That said, there were a few interesting differences, with Rust being much more commonly used in RSE projects connected to doctoral/professional universities than in other contexts.

VIII. FUTURE WORK

We look forward to future work, which remains vast. This includes examining the remaining set of universities in the United States (e.g., master's universities, liberal arts colleges), other government agencies, projects not housed on GitHub, non-open-source RSE projects, tracking change of RSE projects over time, examining counterparts in other nations, and deeper analysis comparing and contrasting the RSE repositories found in each of these distinct domains. For example, answering the question of why R2 universities have more dead RSE projects than their R1 and doctoral counterparts.

APPENDIX

Note: missing R2 and Doctoral/Professional universities from this list indicate the institution’s website did not permit automatic scraping/traversal.

TABLE VI: RQ1 and RQ2 summary results for three Carnegie classes of universities.

University(.edu)	Scraping .edu websites			Searching on GitHub			Scraping \cup Searching		
	Total	RSE	(%)	Total	RSE	(%)	Total	RSE	(%)
All R1	6346	4453	70.2%	187728	30971	16.5%	193921	35361	18.2%
All R2	657	342	52.1%	73080	10651	14.6%	73707	10983	14.9%
All Doctoral	60	24	40.0%	82280	10013	12.2%	82337	10037	12.2%

TABLE VII: RQ1 and RQ2 results for R2 universities.

University(.edu)	Scraping .edu websites			Searching on GitHub			Scraping \cup Searching		
	Total	RSE	(%)	Total	RSE	(%)	Total	RSE	(%)
All	657	342	52.1%	73080	10651	14.6%	73707	10983	14.9%
american	9	2	22.2%	1698	468	27.6%	1705	470	27.6%
astate	2	0	0.0%	96	3	3.1%	98	3	3.1%
augusta	0	0	0.0%	583	25	4.3%	583	25	4.3%
bgsu	1	0	0.0%	196	34	17.3%	196	34	17.3%
boisestate	7	5	71.4%	238	38	16.0%	245	43	17.6%
byu	6	3	50.0%	1194	98	8.2%	1199	100	8.3%
chapman	3	2	66.7%	959	120	12.5%	961	121	12.6%
charlotte	16	9	56.2%	1334	90	6.7%	1349	99	7.3%
clarkson	4	2	50.0%	384	43	11.2%	388	45	11.6%
clarku	7	6	85.7%	155	26	16.8%	162	32	19.8%
creighton	0	0	0.0%	193	7	3.6%	193	7	3.6%
csueastbay	6	1	16.7%	35	6	17.1%	41	7	17.1%
csulb	0	0	0.0%	736	42	5.7%	736	42	5.7%
csuohio	2	1	50.0%	58	6	10.3%	60	7	11.7%
csusb	5	3	60.0%	265	22	8.3%	270	25	9.3%
depaul	1	0	0.0%	1005	68	6.8%	1006	68	6.8%
duq	1	0	0.0%	1017	54	5.3%	1018	54	5.3%
ecu	6	5	83.3%	1039	175	16.8%	1045	180	17.2%
esf	9	8	88.9%	1002	93	9.3%	1011	101	10.0%
etsu	5	2	40.0%	274	11	4.0%	279	13	4.7%
famu	0	0	0.0%	482	54	11.2%	482	54	11.2%
fau	2	2	100.0%	1083	396	36.6%	1085	398	36.7%
fit	8	5	62.5%	1210	382	31.6%	1218	387	31.8%
fordham	7	3	42.9%	269	26	9.7%	276	29	10.5%
fresnostate	3	0	0.0%	30	0	0.0%	33	0	0.0%
georgiasouthern	0	0	0.0%	54	6	11.1%	54	6	11.1%
howard	0	0	0.0%	2141	321	15.0%	2141	321	15.0%
iit	44	20	45.5%	1445	202	14.0%	1489	222	14.9%
illinoisstate	0	0	0.0%	63	9	14.3%	63	9	14.3%
isu	0	0	0.0%	1024	56	5.5%	1024	56	5.5%
iu	4	3	75.0%	1095	174	15.9%	1099	177	16.1%
iup	0	0	0.0%	1003	103	10.3%	1003	103	10.3%
jefferson	0	0	0.0%	1061	38	3.6%	1061	38	3.6%
jmu	1	0	0.0%	1052	57	5.4%	1053	57	5.4%
jsums	0	0	0.0%	19	0	0.0%	19	0	0.0%

TABLE VII: RQ1 and RQ2 results for R2 universities.

University(.edu)	Scraping .edu websites			Searching on GitHub			Scraping \cup Searching		
	Total	RSE	(%)	Total	RSE	(%)	Total	RSE	(%)
kennesaw	22	7	31.8%	1206	48	4.0%	1227	55	4.5%
lehigh	1	1	100.0%	499	66	13.2%	500	67	13.4%
liu	1	0	0.0%	1013	284	28.0%	1014	284	28.0%
llu	0	0	0.0%	1005	47	4.7%	1005	47	4.7%
lmu	10	0	0.0%	1077	118	11.0%	1087	118	10.9%
luc	4	0	0.0%	1222	179	14.6%	1225	179	14.6%
marquette	21	14	66.7%	263	19	7.2%	284	33	11.6%
marshall	0	0	0.0%	1039	55	5.3%	1039	55	5.3%
miamioh	10	1	10.0%	31	4	12.9%	41	5	12.2%
montclair	0	0	0.0%	201	8	4.0%	201	8	4.0%
morgan	1	1	100.0%	1031	69	6.7%	1032	70	6.8%
mst	6	4	66.7%	1048	342	32.6%	1054	346	32.8%
nau	77	41	53.2%	1128	143	12.7%	1205	184	15.3%
ncat	0	0	0.0%	668	120	18.0%	668	120	18.0%
niu	4	2	50.0%	1070	52	4.9%	1073	53	4.9%
nmsu	0	0	0.0%	259	36	13.9%	259	36	13.9%
nova	1	0	0.0%	1074	110	10.2%	1075	110	10.2%
rit	63	42	66.7%	1226	182	14.8%	1285	223	17.4%
rowan	1	1	100.0%	1155	88	7.6%	1156	89	7.7%
sdstate	5	3	60.0%	39	7	17.9%	43	10	23.3%
sfsu	2	2	100.0%	856	67	7.8%	858	69	8.0%
shsu	1	1	100.0%	150	14	9.3%	151	15	9.9%
siu	0	0	0.0%	1012	46	4.5%	1012	46	4.5%
slu	2	0	0.0%	1112	346	31.1%	1114	346	31.1%
smu	4	1	25.0%	1089	194	17.8%	1093	195	17.8%
southalabama	1	0	0.0%	18	3	16.7%	19	3	15.8%
tamucc	1	0	0.0%	48	7	14.6%	49	7	14.3%
tarleton	2	0	0.0%	2043	431	21.1%	2045	431	21.1%
tcu	0	0	0.0%	1008	73	7.2%	1008	73	7.2%
tnstate	1	1	100.0%	45	5	11.1%	46	6	13.0%
tntech	2	0	0.0%	2383	168	7.0%	2385	168	7.0%
tsu	0	0	0.0%	1014	157	15.5%	1014	157	15.5%
txst	2	0	0.0%	2852	592	20.8%	2853	592	20.8%
uaf	2	0	0.0%	878	122	13.9%	879	122	13.9%
uakron	2	1	50.0%	40	4	10.0%	42	5	11.9%
uccs	0	0	0.0%	987	114	11.6%	987	114	11.6%
udayton	6	4	66.7%	54	9	16.7%	60	13	21.7%
uidaho	25	5	20.0%	302	63	20.9%	325	68	20.9%
umassd	15	11	73.3%	164	31	18.9%	178	41	23.0%
umb	7	4	57.1%	1045	98	9.4%	1052	102	9.7%
umkc	0	0	0.0%	548	39	7.1%	548	39	7.1%
uml	19	13	68.4%	1064	307	28.9%	1083	320	29.5%
umsl	0	0	0.0%	435	26	6.0%	435	26	6.0%
uncg	0	0	0.0%	174	16	9.2%	174	16	9.2%
uncw	4	4	100.0%	1356	245	18.1%	1360	249	18.3%
und	2	2	100.0%	1099	293	26.7%	1101	295	26.8%
une	2	1	50.0%	1054	632	60.0%	1056	633	59.9%
unf	2	0	0.0%	1031	181	17.6%	1033	181	17.5%
uno	1	0	0.0%	1067	153	14.3%	1068	153	14.3%
unomaha	7	2	28.6%	74	13	17.6%	80	15	18.8%

TABLE VII: RQ1 and RQ2 results for R2 universities.

University(.edu)	Scraping .edu websites			Searching on GitHub			Scraping \cup Searching		
	Total	RSE (%)	(%)	Total	RSE (%)	(%)	Total	RSE (%)	(%)
uprrp	2	1	50.0%	34	4	11.8%	36	5	13.9%
uri	7	6	85.7%	1084	211	19.5%	1091	217	19.9%
utrgv	0	0	0.0%	121	16	13.2%	121	16	13.2%
uttyler	0	0	0.0%	42	5	11.9%	42	5	11.9%
uvm	11	6	54.5%	1076	261	24.3%	1086	266	24.5%
wcupa	0	0	0.0%	550	19	3.5%	550	19	3.5%
wfu	1	1	100.0%	576	55	9.5%	577	56	9.7%
wichita	6	1	16.7%	1324	65	4.9%	1329	66	5.0%
wilmu	0	0	0.0%	78	0	0.0%	78	0	0.0%
wm	1	0	0.0%	1022	212	20.7%	1023	212	20.7%
wmich	3	0	0.0%	611	49	8.0%	614	49	8.0%
wpi	138	75	54.3%	1152	169	14.7%	1290	244	18.9%
wright	3	1	33.3%	1007	138	13.7%	1010	139	13.8%

TABLE VIII: RQ1 and RQ2 results for Doctoral/Professional universities.

University(.edu)	Scraping .edu websites			Searching on GitHub			Scraping \cup Searching		
	Total	RSE (%)	(%)	Total	RSE (%)	(%)	Total	RSE (%)	(%)
All	60	24	40.0%	82280	10013	12.2%	82337	10037	12.2%
acu	1	0	0.0%	1018	124	12.2%	1019	124	12.2%
adelphi	0	0	0.0%	118	9	7.6%	118	9	7.6%
aic	0	0	0.0%	1154	412	35.7%	1154	412	35.7%
alasu	0	0	0.0%	17	2	11.8%	17	2	11.8%
alvernia	0	0	0.0%	15	0	0.0%	15	0	0.0%
andrews	0	0	0.0%	1171	89	7.6%	1171	89	7.6%
aurora	0	0	0.0%	1047	215	20.5%	1047	215	20.5%
barry	0	0	0.0%	1014	26	2.6%	1014	26	2.6%
belhaven	0	0	0.0%	17	0	0.0%	17	0	0.0%
bellarmino	0	0	0.0%	140	2	1.4%	140	2	1.4%
belmont	4	3	75.0%	388	9	2.3%	392	12	3.1%
bethel	0	0	0.0%	1003	7	0.7%	1003	7	0.7%
biola	0	0	0.0%	661	118	17.9%	661	118	17.9%
bradley	0	0	0.0%	1052	69	6.6%	1052	69	6.6%
briarcliff	0	0	0.0%	4	0	0.0%	4	0	0.0%
caluniversity	0	0	0.0%	1	0	0.0%	1	0	0.0%
campbell	0	0	0.0%	1017	83	8.2%	1017	83	8.2%
captechu	2	1	50.0%	20	0	0.0%	22	1	4.5%
chatham	0	0	0.0%	149	7	4.7%	149	7	4.7%
ciis	0	0	0.0%	457	35	7.7%	457	35	7.7%
cityu	0	0	0.0%	741	77	10.4%	741	77	10.4%
clarke	0	0	0.0%	1004	28	2.8%	1004	28	2.8%
css	0	0	0.0%	1715	35	2.0%	1715	35	2.0%
cuw	0	0	0.0%	326	27	8.3%	326	27	8.3%
daemen	0	0	0.0%	17	5	29.4%	17	5	29.4%
desales	1	0	0.0%	36	3	8.3%	37	3	8.1%
drake	2	0	0.0%	1057	162	15.3%	1059	162	15.3%
dyu	0	0	0.0%	725	21	2.9%	725	21	2.9%
edgewood	0	0	0.0%	47	0	0.0%	47	0	0.0%

TABLE VIII: RQ1 and RQ2 results for Doctoral/Professional universities.

University(.edu)	Scraping .edu websites			Searching on GitHub			Scraping \cup Searching		
	Total	RSE (%)		Total	RSE (%)		Total	RSE (%)	
eku	0	0	0.0%	1011	42	4.2%	1011	42	4.2%
elon	0	0	0.0%	1027	44	4.3%	1027	44	4.3%
fairfield	0	0	0.0%	275	8	2.9%	275	8	2.9%
ferris	1	1	100.0%	1015	38	3.7%	1016	39	3.8%
fgcu	0	0	0.0%	157	21	13.4%	157	21	13.4%
fielding	0	0	0.0%	1317	421	32.0%	1317	421	32.0%
georgefox	0	0	0.0%	894	51	5.7%	894	51	5.7%
gmercycu	0	0	0.0%	2	0	0.0%	2	0	0.0%
gonzaga	4	0	0.0%	600	21	3.5%	604	21	3.5%
hamptonu	0	0	0.0%	17	1	5.9%	17	1	5.9%
harding	0	0	0.0%	434	16	3.7%	434	16	3.7%
hartford	0	0	0.0%	1315	92	7.0%	1315	92	7.0%
hofstra	1	1	100.0%	107	16	15.0%	108	17	15.7%
husson	0	0	0.0%	32	3	9.4%	32	3	9.4%
indstate	0	0	0.0%	40	5	12.5%	40	5	12.5%
indwes	0	0	0.0%	416	13	3.1%	416	13	3.1%
kean	0	0	0.0%	1053	28	2.7%	1053	28	2.7%
lamar	0	0	0.0%	1013	47	4.6%	1013	47	4.6%
lasalle	0	0	0.0%	1027	31	3.0%	1027	31	3.0%
laverne	0	0	0.0%	85	3	3.5%	85	3	3.5%
lesley	1	0	0.0%	523	5	1.0%	524	5	1.0%
liberty	1	0	0.0%	1104	73	6.6%	1105	73	6.6%
lipscomb	0	0	0.0%	54	2	3.7%	54	2	3.7%
lmunet	0	0	0.0%	1000	113	11.3%	1000	113	11.3%
marian	0	0	0.0%	1027	92	9.0%	1027	92	9.0%
maryville	1	1	100.0%	223	8	3.6%	224	9	4.0%
masters	0	0	0.0%	1052	165	15.7%	1052	165	15.7%
mc	0	0	0.0%	1159	395	34.1%	1159	395	34.1%
missouristate	2	1	50.0%	15	1	6.7%	17	2	11.8%
msj	0	0	0.0%	2862	302	10.6%	2862	302	10.6%
national	0	0	0.0%	1087	402	37.0%	1087	402	37.0%
nku	1	0	0.0%	1035	70	6.8%	1036	70	6.8%
okcu	0	0	0.0%	555	95	17.1%	555	95	17.1%
ollusa	0	0	0.0%	45	5	11.1%	45	5	11.1%
pace	0	0	0.0%	1247	285	22.9%	1247	285	22.9%
pacificu	0	0	0.0%	3237	486	15.0%	3237	486	15.0%
pba	0	0	0.0%	1010	108	10.7%	1010	108	10.7%
pepperdine	3	0	0.0%	41	2	4.9%	43	2	4.7%
phoenix	0	0	0.0%	1026	128	12.5%	1026	128	12.5%
pointpark	2	0	0.0%	29	3	10.3%	31	3	9.7%
pucpr	0	0	0.0%	1000	30	3.0%	1000	30	3.0%
radford	1	0	0.0%	199	38	19.1%	200	38	19.0%
regent	1	0	0.0%	565	73	12.9%	566	73	12.9%
regis	0	0	0.0%	3992	493	12.3%	3992	493	12.3%
rmu	0	0	0.0%	1015	73	7.2%	1015	73	7.2%
roosevelt	0	0	0.0%	515	58	11.3%	515	58	11.3%
saintleo	0	0	0.0%	12	2	16.7%	12	2	16.7%
samford	1	0	0.0%	42	1	2.4%	43	1	2.3%
sau	0	0	0.0%	1052	131	12.5%	1052	131	12.5%

TABLE VIII: RQ1 and RQ2 results for Doctoral/Professional universities.

University(.edu)	Scraping .edu websites			Searching on GitHub			Scraping \cup Searching		
	Total	RSE (%)		Total	RSE (%)		Total	RSE (%)	
scu	10	5	50.0%	1323	257	19.4%	1333	262	19.7%
seattleu	0	0	0.0%	1313	105	8.0%	1313	105	8.0%
seu	0	0	0.0%	1076	156	14.5%	1076	156	14.5%
siue	0	0	0.0%	160	19	11.9%	160	19	11.9%
sjf	0	0	0.0%	2001	419	20.9%	2001	419	20.9%
south	0	0	0.0%	1150	204	17.7%	1150	204	17.7%
southuniversity	0	0	0.0%	2	0	0.0%	2	0	0.0%
springfield	0	0	0.0%	661	43	6.5%	661	43	6.5%
spu	0	0	0.0%	1032	179	17.3%	1032	179	17.3%
stfrancis	0	0	0.0%	66	4	6.1%	66	4	6.1%
stkate	0	0	0.0%	2	0	0.0%	2	0	0.0%
stockton	0	0	0.0%	238	13	5.5%	238	13	5.5%
stthom	0	0	0.0%	86	12	14.0%	86	12	14.0%
tamuc	1	1	100.0%	123	10	8.1%	124	11	8.9%
touro	0	0	0.0%	11	2	18.2%	11	2	18.2%
trevecca	0	0	0.0%	9	1	11.1%	9	1	11.1%
twu	0	0	0.0%	2	0	0.0%	2	0	0.0%
uagm	0	0	0.0%	14	3	21.4%	14	3	21.4%
uca	0	0	0.0%	1040	181	17.4%	1040	181	17.4%
ucumberlands	0	0	0.0%	12	2	16.7%	12	2	16.7%
ulm	1	0	0.0%	1008	234	23.2%	1009	234	23.2%
umary	0	0	0.0%	791	108	13.7%	791	108	13.7%
unco	0	0	0.0%	1033	192	18.6%	1033	192	18.6%
upike	0	0	0.0%	10	0	0.0%	10	0	0.0%
usfca	11	5	45.5%	285	46	16.1%	295	51	17.3%
uu	0	0	0.0%	1253	169	13.5%	1253	169	13.5%
uwosh	1	1	100.0%	97	9	9.3%	98	10	10.2%
valdosta	0	0	0.0%	2038	249	12.2%	2038	249	12.2%
valpo	4	1	25.0%	1192	96	8.1%	1195	97	8.1%
walsh	0	0	0.0%	989	143	14.5%	989	143	14.5%
wcu	1	1	100.0%	1547	141	9.1%	1548	142	9.2%
westga	1	0	0.0%	143	5	3.5%	144	5	3.5%
widener	0	0	0.0%	387	41	10.6%	387	41	10.6%
wilkes	0	0	0.0%	144	25	17.4%	144	25	17.4%
williamwoods	0	0	0.0%	1771	121	6.8%	1771	121	6.8%
wku	2	1	50.0%	0	0	0.0%	2	1	50.0%
wmcarey	0	0	0.0%	1	0	0.0%	1	0	0.0%
wne	0	0	0.0%	682	77	11.3%	682	77	11.3%
xavier	0	0	0.0%	3045	500	16.4%	3045	500	16.4%
yu	1	1	100.0%	1197	181	15.1%	1198	182	15.2%

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